

THE PLACENTA AS AN ENDOCRINE ORGAN CONTROLS PREGNANCY

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During pregnancy, the placenta produces major protein hormones, each of which is biologically and immunologically similar to pituitary and hypothalamic hormones. Those similar to the hypothalamic hormones produced by the placenta include: gonadotropin-releasing, corticotropin-releasing, thyrotropin-releasing hormone, and somatotropin. Similar to pituitary hormones: chorionic gonadotropin, placental lactogen, chorionic corticotropin, adrenocorticotrophic hormone. In addition, the following growth factors are produced: insulin-like growth factor (IGF-1), epidermal growth factor (EGF), platelet growth factor (PGF), fibroblast growth factor (FGF), transforming growth factor R (TGFP), inhibin, activin. The following are synthesized from cytokines: interleukin-1 (IL-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6), colony-stimulating factor 1 (CSF1).

Pregnancy-specific proteins: beta1 - glycoprotein (SR1), eosinophil major protein rMVR, soluble proteins RR1-20, membrane binding proteins and enzymes. Proteins produced by the mother's organism, that is, by the decidual tissue: prolactin, relaxin, insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGFBP-1), interleukin 1, colony-stimulating factor 1 (CSF-1), progesterone-associated endometrial protein.

Chorionic gonadotropin is the main hormone of pregnancy, its glycoprotein composition is similar to lactotropic hormone (LG). Like all glycoproteins, it consists of alpha and beta chains. The alpha chain is identical to all glycoproteins, and the beta chain is identical to every hormone. Chorionic gonadotropin is synthesized by syncytiotrophoblasts. The alpha chain of this hormone is controlled by a gene located on chromosome 6, and the beta chain is controlled by a gene on chromosome 19. Chorionic gonadotropin appears on the 8th day after ovulation, on the 1st day after implantation under the influence of sex hormones, releasing factors, growth factors, inhibin and activin.

The activity of chorionic gonadotropin is multifaceted: it controls the development and functioning of the corpus luteum until the 7th week of pregnancy, affects the adrenal gland and sperm testosterone. Human chorionic gonadotropin gene expression has been detected in the kidney and adrenal gland from fetal tissues, thus confirming the involvement of these organs in growth. Receptors for chorionic gonadotropin are found in the myometrium and

its vessels, so this hormone controls the uterus and its vascularization. The maximum amount of chorionic gonadotropin is observed in the 8-10th week of pregnancy, and its amount is 100,000 IU, then it decreases, and in the 16th week, 1000-2000 IU, this amount remains until the 34th week of pregnancy. After the 34th week of pregnancy, the second peak period of hormone growth is observed. Its daily production amount is 1 gram.

According to Kaplan S., placental lactogen is the main metabolic hormone, which provides nutrition to the fetus, and its amount increases in the later stages of pregnancy. Placental lactogen is an insulin antagonist. Ketone bodies are the main source of energy in the fetus. Increased ketogenesis occurs due to a decrease in the amount of insulin under the influence of placental lactogen. As a result, the utilization of glucose in the mother slows down, and the supply of glucose to the fetus increases. Chorionic growth hormone is produced by syncytiotrophoblasts and is detected in the mother's blood only in the II trimester of pregnancy, and its amount increases until the 36th week. Its biological effect is similar to placental lactogen.

The placenta produces a large number of peptide hormones whose mechanism of action is similar to pituitary and hypothalamic hormones, including: chorionic thyrotropin, chorionic adrenocorticotropin, chorionic gonadotropin, and releasing hormone. The mechanism of these hormones of the placenta is not fully revealed, they can also act in a paracrine way, similar to the hormones of the pituitary and hypothalamus. Recently, there has been increasing attention to the effects of placental corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH).

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